

Big Data to Enable Global Disruption of the Grapevine-powered Industries

D6.2 - Platform Operational Report

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ACRONYMS LIST

BDG	BigDataGrapes
DSS	Decision support system
API	Application Programming Interface
UI	User Interface
TARQL	Tabular SPARQL
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
RDF	Resource Description Framework
CES	Concept Extraction Service
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Big Data Platform developed in the BigDataGrapes project, is a distributed platform that follows a microservices-based architecture, in order to support a large number of different use cases that are using highly heterogeneous, dynamic and large datasets. It is offering a set of REST APIs that enable end users to a) discover the supported data sets and the included instance classes with their corresponding properties; b) semantically annotate large unstructured documents with configurable information extraction pipelines; c) execute advanced searches on the data stored in the BigDataGrapes knowledgebase and d) visualize the result in various formats.

In the context of the project, an operational instance of the Big Data Platform was used to support 5 pilots of the grapevine industry. The instance of the data platform was monitored to identify any performance issues during the support of the pilots. The monitoring results of the operational instance indicated that there were no performance issues during the ingestion, processing, enrichment, indexing and visualization of the data used in the 5 pilots.

In this report we are providing information about the platform's operation and resource usage for the reporting period, indicating all the details about its operation for the different layers of the platform. We also provide a set of guidelines and good practices for managing and maintaining a BigDataGrapes platform deployment for the real world scenarios of the agrifood sector.

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1 Introduction

The BigDataGrapes (BDG) platform aims at targeting the needs of the grapevine industry using Big Data technologies, frameworks and components. In this document we perform an operational report over the current state of the BDG stack, as described in D2.3.

We conduct the operational report by initially provided an abstract overview of the architecture. We then drill down to each of the stack's layers, depicting each components' and describing them in high detail. We chose to describe each of the components by describing the API endpoints of each, following the microservice architecture that has been chosen for the BDG stack.

It should be noted that all of this report is done on the working version of the BDG stack, with the currently deployed and usable components and tools and is expected to increase in the future to cover more, as they are completed and integrated.

We present the approach on how the BigDataGrapes is monitored to identify possible issues during the operation in section 4. In the last section we provide a set of guidelines and good practices for managing and maintaining a BigDataPlatform deployment covering issues like set up, orchestrating all the components, identification of data records and automating data engineering tasks.

2 BigDataGrapes Platform Operation

2.1 OVERVIEW DIAGRAM

Figure 1: Figure 1: High level architecture of BDG platform.

Figure 1 illustrates an abstract overview of the complete BDG platform. As further analyzed in D2.3, the platform is split into multiple layers, based on their usage. As described in more detail in the following sections, the connection between the different layers is performed through API endpoints following the principles of a microservice architecture.

2.2 DATA FLOWS & WRAPPER API(S)

The whole is designed, implemented and deployed in a microservice architecture. As a result, all of the communication between the layers and the frameworks is performed through API endpoints and Apache Nifi

dataflows. To facilitate this decision a number of endpoints and different services have been implemented connecting the various layers and technologies employed for the design of the BDG stack.

This section is organised in the following manner: we start by presenting each layer separately, giving an abstract description of it. We drill down for each layer presenting the different API endpoints that are employed for each, along with the involved technologies/frameworks.

2.2.1 Persistence Layer

The persistence layer is the one responsible with the storage of the provided or generated data throughout the BDG stack. It consists of various storage engines that are employed depending on the kind of data that will be stored and has a number of wrapper API endpoints to facilitate the creation/update or search of the data stored.

2.2.1.1 Supported Datasets API

We provide three controllers for managing the supported datasets. The first one is for managing the existing repositories that can contain different datasets. The second one is for keeping track of the contexts within repositories, for keeping track of different supported datasets that exist within one repository. The third one is the namespaces controller that helps us tidy the datasets and their URIs within prefixed namespaces.

2.2.1.1.1 Repositories

The repositories-management controller provides the possibility to create, delete and modify repositories as well as to view current configuration and statistics about existing ones. This functionality is divided among a total of 8 endpoints.

[/rest/repositories - GET](#)

Provides a list of the existing repositories and their respective configurations.

Table 1: Repository parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
location	Filter results by given location	query	string	yes	None (get from all locations)

Sample response:

```

    {
      "head": {
        "vars": [
          "uri",
          "id",
          "title",
          "readable",
          "writable"
        ]
      },
      "results": {
        "bindings": [
          {
            "readable": {
              "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#boolean",
              "type": "literal",
              "value": "true"
            },
            "id": {
              "type": "literal",
              "value": "bdg-datasets"
            },
            "title": {
              "type": "literal",
              "value": "bdg-datasets"
            },
            "uri": {
              "type": "uri",
              "value": "http://136.243.38.67:7200/repositories/bdg-datasets"
            },
            "writable": {
              "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#boolean",
              "type": "literal",
              "value": "true"
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  
```

Figure 2: A sample response of the /rest/repositories - GET endpoint

/rest/repositories - POST

Creates a new repository using a given turtle file that contains the configuration.

Table 2: New repository parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
config	turtle file containing the repository configuration	formData	file	No	
location	location for the repository	query	string	Yes	

Sample config:

```
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>.
@prefix rep: <http://www.openrdf.org/config/repository#>.
@prefix sr: <http://www.openrdf.org/config/repository/sail#>.
@prefix sail: <http://www.openrdf.org/config/sail#>.
@prefix owl: <http://www.ontotext.com/tree/owlim#>.
```

```
    [] a rep:Repository ;
      rep:repositoryID "repo1" ;
      rdfs:label "my repository number one" ;
      rep:repositoryImpl [
        rep:repositoryType "graphdb:FreeSailRepository" ;
        sr:sailImpl [
          sail:sailType "graphdb:FreeSail" ;

          owl:owlim-license "" ;

          owlim:base-URL "http://example.org/graphdb#" ;
          owlim:defaultNS "" ;
          owlim:entity-index-size "200000" ;
          owlim:entity-id-size "32" ;
          owlim:imports "" ;
          owlim:repository-type "file-repository" ;
          owlim:ruleset "owl-horst-optimized" ;
          owlim:storage-folder "storage" ;

          owlim:enable-context-index "false" ;
          owlim:cache-memory "80m" ;
          owlim:tuple-index-memory "80m" ;

          owlim:enablePredicateList "false" ;
          owlim:predicate-memory "0%" ;

          owlim:fts-memory "0%" ;
          owlim:ftsIndexPolicy "never" ;
          owlim:ftsLiteralsOnly "true" ;

          owlim:in-memory-literal-properties "false" ;
          owlim:enable-literal-index "true" ;
          owlim:index-compression-ratio "-1" ;

          owlim:check-for-inconsistencies "false" ;
          owlim:disable-sameAs "false" ;
          owlim:enable-optimization "true" ;
```

```

        owl:transaction-mode "safe" ;
        owl:transaction-isolation "true" ;
        owl:query-timeout "0" ;
        owl:query-limit-results "0" ;
        owl:throw-QueryEvaluationException-on-timeout "false" ;
        owl:useShutdownHooks "true" ;
        owl:read-only "false" ;
        owl:nonInterpretablePredicates "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-
        schema#label;http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-
        ns#type;http://www.ontotext.com/owlim/ces#gazetteerConfig;http://www.ontotext.com/owlim/ces#metad
        ataConfig" ;
    ]
].

```

Figure 3: A sample config for the /rest/repositories - POST endpoint

/rest/repositories - PUT

For creating a new repository by providing a json with the configuration.

Table 3: Parameters for new repository creation with JSON

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
body	JSON with the repo config	body		No	

Sample body:

```

{
  "id": "repo1",
  "location": "",
  "params": {},
  "sesameType": "owlim:ReplicationClusterWorker",
  "title": "my repository number one",
  "type": "worker"
}

```

Figure 4: A sample body of a request sent to /rest/repositories - PUT endpoint

/rest/repositories/{repositoryId} - DELETE

Deletes a repository by given id.

Table 4: Parameters for deleting a repository

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryId	the id of the repository that will be deleted	path	string	no	
location	Specify repository location	query	string	yes	None

[/rest/repositories/{repositoryId} - GET](#)

Retrieve repository configuration by id.

Table 5: Repository configuration retrieval parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryId	Id of the repository for which the config will be fetched	path	string	no	
location	for specifying the location.	query	string	yes	None

Sample response:

```

    {
      "id": "bdg-datasets",
      "title": "bdg-datasets",
      "type": "free",
      "sesameType": "graphdb:FreeSailRepository",
      "location": "",
      "params": {
        "queryTimeout": {
          "label": "Query time-out (seconds)",
          "name": "queryTimeout",
          "value": "0"
        },
        "imports": {
          "label": "Imported RDF files('; ' delimited)",
          "name": "imports",
          "value": ""
        },
        "inMemoryLiteralProperties": {
          "label": "Cache literal language tags",
          "name": "inMemoryLiteralProperties",
          "value": "true"
        },
        "ruleset": {
          "label": "Ruleset",
          "name": "ruleset",
          "value": "rdfsplus-optimized"
        },
        "readOnly": {
          "label": "Read-only",
          "name": "readOnly",
          "value": "false"
        },
        "checkForInconsistencies": {
          "label": "Check for inconsistencies",
          "name": "checkForInconsistencies",
          "value": "false"
        },
        "disableSameAs": {
          "label": "Disable owl:sameAs",
          "name": "disableSameAs",
          "value": "true"
        },
        "enableLiteralIndex": {

```

```

        "label": "Enable literal index",
        "name": "enableLiteralIndex",
        "value": "true"
    },
    "entityIndexSize": {
        "label": "Entity index size",
        "name": "entityIndexSize",
        "value": "10000000"
    },
    "defaultNS": {
"label": "Default namespaces for imports('; delimited)",
        "name": "defaultNS",
        "value": ""
    },
    "enableContextIndex": {
        "label": "Use context index",
        "name": "enableContextIndex",
        "value": "false"
    },
    "baseURL": {
        "label": "Base URL",
        "name": "baseURL",
        "value": "http://example.org/owlim#"
    },
    "queryLimitResults": {
        "label": "Limit query results",
        "name": "queryLimitResults",
        "value": "0"
    },
    "entityIdSize": {
        "label": "Entity ID bit-size",
        "name": "entityIdSize",
        "value": "32"
    },
    "throwQueryEvaluationExceptionOnTimeout": {
        "label": "Throw exception on query time-out",
        "name": "throwQueryEvaluationExceptionOnTimeout",
        "value": "false"
    },
    "repositoryType": {
        "label": "Repository type",
        "name": "repositoryType",
        "value": "file-repository"
    }

```

```

    },
    "storageFolder": {
      "label": "Storage folder",
      "name": "storageFolder",
      "value": "storage"
    },
    "enablePredicateList": {
      "label": "Use predicate indices",
      "name": "enablePredicateList",
      "value": "true"
    }
  }
}
}

```

Figure 5: A sample response of the /rest/repositories/{repositoryId} - GET endpoint

/rest/repositories/{repositoryId} - PUT

Edit a repository configuration by providing a json with the new config.

Table 6: Repository editing parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryId	id of the repo that will be reconfigured.	path	string	no	
Bean	JSON containing the new configuration	body	application/json	no	None

Sample body:

```

{
  "id": "repo1",
  "location": "",
  "params": {},
  "sesameType": "owlim:ReplicationClusterWorker",
  "title": "my repository number one",
  "type": "worker"
}

```

Figure 6: A sample body of a request sent to /rest/repositories/{repositoryId} - PUT endpoint

[/rest/repositories/{repositoryId}/download](#)

Download a turtle file that contains the configuration of a given repository

Table 7: Downloading repository configuration in turtle

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryId	id of the repo whose configuration will be downloaded	path	string	no	None
location	for specifying the location.	query	string	yes	None

[/rest/repositories/{repositoryId}/size](#)

Retrieve the number of inferred, explicit and total statements in a given repository.

Table 8: Repository statistics retrieval parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryId	Id of the repo	path	string	no	
location	for specifying the location.	query	string	yes	

Sample response:

```
{
  "inferred": 164,
  "total": 33362924,
  "explicit": 33362760
}
```

Figure 7: A sample response of the [/rest/repositories/{repositoryId}/size](#) endpoint

2.2.1.1.2 Contexts

[/repositories/{repositoryID}/contexts - GET](#)

This endpoint provides a list of contextes within a given repository.

Table 9: Repository contexts list

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryID	ID of the repo for which the contextes will be retrieved	path	string	no	

Sample response body:

```
    {
      "head": {
        "vars": [
          "contextID"
        ]
      },
      "results": {
        "bindings": [
          {
            "contextID": {
              "type": "uri",
              "value": "http://linkedlifedata.com/resource/dailymed/"
            }
          },
          {
            "contextID": {
              "type": "uri",
              "value": "http://linkedlifedata.com/resource/pubmed"
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  }
```

Figure 8: A sample response of the [/repositories/{repositoryId}/contexts - GET](#) endpoint

2.2.1.1.3 Namespaces

The namespace controller manages prefixes and their associated namespaces.

[/repositories/{repositoryID}/namespaces/{namespacesPrefix} - GET](#)

Resolves a given prefix to a namespace within a given repo.

Table 10: Namespecase definition parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryID	working repository	path	string	no	
namespacePrefix	URI prefix that will be resolved	path	string	no	

Sample response body (for rdf prefix):

```
http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#
```

Figure 9: A sample response of the [/repositories/{repositoryId}/namespaces{namespacesPrefix} - GET](#) endpoint

[/repositories/{repositoryID}/namespaces/{namespacesPrefix} - PUT](#)

Creates a new prefix for a given namespace.

Table 11: New namespaces definition parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryID	working repository	path	string	no	
namespacePrefix	new namespace prefix	path	string	no	
	the resolved value for the prefix	body	string	no	

/repositories/{repositoryID}/namespaces/{namespacesPrefix} - DELETE

Deletes a given prefix for a given repository.

Table 12: Parameters for deletion of namespaces for a repository

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryID	working repository	path	string	no	
namespacePrefix	prefix that will be deleted	path	string	no	

2.2.1.2 Field Registry Service

The field registry service consists of endpoints responsible for the storage and search of fields, along with metadata information. Requests to this endpoint are made either through Apache Nifi's dataflows or by using the respective UI for each pilot. In the current state of the BDG stack, this service is implemented using Java and Spring Boot.

This service is split into 2 different operations along with the respective endpoints. One which is responsible for the storage of the information on fields and another where one can search on the stored data by providing filters on it.

Table 13 shows the required input format for the creation or update of a field stored into the BDG stack.

Table 13: Create/Update field parameters

Parameter	Description	Required
id	The id of the field to be created or updated. In case it is not existent, the service will automatically assign a new, if existent the service will create it with the supplied one, which if already present in the storage engine an update of the values with the provided will happen.	no
crop	The crop that is cultivated in the field. Since it is a metadata	no

	description on the field, it is not a required value.	
name	The name of the field. The provided value is how the field will be displayed the visualization layer of the stack making it a required parameter.	yes
parcel	This is the value that links the field with the information stored into Geoclidean's service. Although not required, if not present any models in the support layer that need this data will not be able to fully link the provided datasets.	yes

Requests to this endpoint are made using PUT and expect a JSON as content type of the input, provided in the body of the HTTP request. Once the creation or update of the field is complete, the endpoints responds with a JSON with the values that were actually stored into the stack. As is the case with all of the services, the metadata information is stored into MongoDB, while the actual data into Elasticsearch. Figure 10 shows a sample of the expected input and the output schema for this specific endpoint.

```
[
  {
    "crop": "string",
    "id": "string",
    "name": "string",
    "parcelId": 0
  }
]
```

Figure 10: The JSON schema expected by Field Registry Service

2.2.1.3 Field Indicator Service

The field indicator service is the one responsible with the creation and update of data concerning environmental and sensor readings for a specific field. Requests to this service can be made either through the offline cron tasks, by the respective UI for each pilot or by using the API endpoint directly. Currently this service is implemented using Java and Spring Boot, sending and reading data from MongoDB, Elasticsearch and Apache Cassandra based on the type of data that is to be stored. More specifically MongoDB stores all the metadata information, such as the type of indicator the value read is about, Apache Cassandra is used for the initial storage of information to take advantage of its very high write throughput and Elasticsearch has all the actual data, following their insert into Apache Cassandra.

This service has 2 main operations: creation/update of information and searching capabilities using filters.

Table 14 shows the required format of requests made to this service. All of the requests are done to the respective endpoints either by providing a JSON request in the body in case of a creation or update, or by URL parameters in case of a search.

Table 14: Indicator service request parameters

Parameter	Description	Required
id	<p>The id of the field to be created or updated.</p> <p>In case it is not existent, the service will automatically assign a new, if existent the service will create it with the supplied one, which if already present in the storage engine an update of the values with the provided will happen.</p>	no
belongsToIn	<p>This is an object that refers to the field for which the indicator is about.</p> <p>The format of this field is as described in the previous section.</p>	yes
value	The actual value of the indicator	yes
date	The date with optional time information for which the indicator was read	yes
name	The name of the indicator read (eg. Relative Humidity)	yes
pilot	<p>The pilot for which the value is about.</p> <p>If not present the platform will attempt to link it offline with the rest of the metadata information provided.</p>	no
maxValue	<p>The max value read for this indicator at the specific date.</p> <p>This is an expansion of the initial schema to cover the data provided by GEOCLIDEAN.</p>	no
minValue	<p>The minimum value read for this indicator at the specific date.</p> <p>This is an expansion of the initial schema to cover the data provided by GEOCLIDEAN.</p>	no

meanValue	<p>The mean value read for this indicator at the specific date.</p> <p>This is an expansion of the initial schema to cover the data provided by GEOCLIDEAN.</p>	no
stdValue	<p>The standard deviation of values read for this indicator at the specific date.</p> <p>This is an expansion of the initial schema to cover the data provided by GEOCLIDEAN.</p>	no
sumValue	<p>The sum of values read for this indicator at the specific date.</p> <p>This is an expansion of the initial schema to cover the data provided by GEOCLIDEAN.</p>	no
countValue	<p>The number of values read for this indicator at the specific date.</p> <p>This is an expansion of the initial schema to cover the data provided by GEOCLIDEAN.</p>	no
source	<p>The source that provided the information.</p> <p>This is an expansion of the initial schema to cover the data provided by GEOCLIDEAN.</p>	no

In case of a creation or update the requests made to the respective endpoint are PUT requests with the schema described in the Table 14 above and shown in figure 11. In case of a search, a GET request is done, providing any or all of the fields provided by the schema.

```

[
  {
    "belongsIn": {
      "crop": "string",
      "id": "string",
      "name": "string",
      "parcelId": 0
    },
    "countValue": 0,
    "date": "string",
    "id": "string",
    "maxValue": 0,
    "meanValue": 0,
    "minValue": 0,
    "name": "string",
    "pilot": "string",
    "source": "string",
    "stdValue": 0,
    "sumValue": 0,
    "value": 0
  }
]

```

Figure 11: The JSON schema the field indicator service expects

2.2.1.4 Knowledge Graph API

There are two controllers that provide read and write functionality within the knowledge graph. The first one is the Sparql controller which makes it possible to execute Sparql queries against the graph database. The second one is the graph-store controller, which can be used to fetch and insert statements into a named graph within a given repository.

2.2.1.4.1 Sparql

The sparql controller provides two endpoints - one for read oriented SPARQL queries and one for updates. The first one also serves as a SPARQL endpoint that is fully compliant with the SPARQL 1.1 protocol.

[/repositories/{repositoryID} - GET](#)

Returns results for a given SPARQL query

Table 15: SPARQL query parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryID	repository against which the query will be evaluated	path	string	no	

query	Query that will be evaluated	query	string	no	
queryLn	Query language	query	string	yes	sparql
Infer	Whether to include inferred results	query	boolean	yes	true
timeout	Max query execution time in seconds - 0 or negative signifies no limit	query	integer	yes	0
distinct	Whether to return only distinct results	query	boolean	yes	false
limit	Max number of returned results - 0 or negative signifies no limit	query	integer	yes	0
offset	Number of results that will be skipped - 0 or negative signifies no offset	query	integer	yes	0

Sample response (for `select * where{?s ?p ?o.}`)

```

    {
      "head": {
        "vars": [
          "s",
          "p",
          "o"
        ]
      },
      "results": {
        "bindings": [
          {
            "p": {
              "type": "uri",
              "value": "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type"
            },
            "s": {
              "type": "uri",
              "value": "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type"
            },
            "o": {
              "type": "uri",
              "value": "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#Property"
            }
          },
          {
            "p": {
              "type": "uri",
              "value": "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type"
            },
            "s": {
              "type": "uri",
              "value": "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#subPropertyOf"
            },
            "o": {
              "type": "uri",
              "value": "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#Property"
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  
```

Figure 12: A sample response of the /repositories/{repositoryId} endpoint

[/repositories/{repositoryID}/statements - POST](#)

Endpoint for inserting statements into the repository. You can use a SPARQL Update string or an RDF document.

Table 16: RDF insert statements parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryID	repository in which the statements will be inserted	path	string	no	
update	SPARQL update string	query	string	no	
baseURI	Specify base uri for the inserted URIs	query	string	yes	None

2.2.1.4.2 Graph-store

[/repositories/{repositoryID}/rdf-graphs/{graph} - DELETE](#)

Delete a named graph within a repository

Table 17: Delete graph from repository parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryID	Id of the repo from which the graph will be deleted	path	string	no	
graph	URI of the graph that will be deleted	path	string	no	

[/repositories/{repositoryID}/rdf-graphs/{graph} - GET](#)

Fetch all statements from a given named graph

Table 18: Get all statements from a graph in repository parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryID	Id of the repo from which the graph will be fetched	path	string	no	
graph	URI of the graph that will be fetched	path	string	no	

/repositories/{repositoryID}/rdf-graphs/{graph} - POST

Add statements to a given graph.

Table 19: Parameters for inserting a statement in a graph

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repositoryID	Id of the repo from which the graph will be fetched	path	string	no	
graph	URI of the graph that will be fetched	path	string	no	
	Statements that will be inserted in the graph	body	one of the following content types - application/rdf+xml, text/plain, text/turtle, text/rdf+n3, text/x-nquads, application/rdf+json, application/trix, application/x-trig, application/x-binary-rdf.	no	

2.2.2 Ingestion Layer

The ingestion layer is the one responsible with the collection and storage of data aggregated from sensor deployments, files, API endpoints and databases. In the rest of this section we describe the components currently integrated into the BDG stack, responsible for these tasks.

2.2.2.1 RDF data import

For importing RDF data it is recommended to put the files into the database import folder. Once they are there the ingestion can be managed by the ingestion controller which provides the following endpoints.

[/rest/data/import/server/{repository} - GET](#)

Retrieve a list of all files that are ready to import.

Table 20: Parameters for listing files for import

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repository	Name of the repository for which the files can be imported	path	string	no	

Sample response:

```

[
  {
    "name": "file.zip",
    "status": "NONE",
    "message": "",
    "context": null,
    "replaceGraphs": [],
    "baseURI": null,
    "forceSerial": false,
    "type": "file",
    "format": null,
    "data": null,
    "timestamp": 1560954010114,
    "parserSettings": {
      "preserveBNodeIds": false,
      "failOnUnknownDataTypes": false,
      "verifyDataTypeValues": false,
      "normalizeDataTypeValues": false,
      "failOnUnknownLanguageTags": false,
      "verifyLanguageTags": true,
      "normalizeLanguageTags": false,
      "verifyURISyntax": true,
      "verifyRelativeURIs": true,
      "stopOnError": true
    },
    "xRequestIdHeaders": null
  }
]

```

Figure 13: A sample response of the `/rest/data/import/server/{repository}` endpoint

`/rest/data/import/server/{repository}` - POST

Import server files into the repository.

Table 21: Parameters for importing server files in a repository

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repository	Repository where files will be imported	path	string	no	
importBody	JSON import configuration	body	application/json	no	

Sample body:

```
{
  "fileNames": [
    "importfile.ttl"
  ],
  "importSettings": {
    "baseURI": "",
    "context": "",
    "data": "string",
    "forceSerial": true,
    "message": "string",
    "name": "string",
    "parserSettings": {
      "failOnUnknownDataTypes": true,
      "failOnUnknownLanguageTags": true,
      "normalizeDataTypeValues": true,
      "normalizeLanguageTags": true,
      "preserveBNodelds": true,
      "stopOnError": true,
      "verifyDataTypeValues": true,
      "verifyLanguageTags": true,
      "verifyRelativeURIs": true,
      "verifyURISyntax": true
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 14: A sample of a POST request to `/rest/data/import/server/{repository}` endpoint

`/rest/data/import/server/{repository}` - DELETE

Cancel an ongoing file import operation.

Table 22: Parameters for canceling file import in a repository

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
repository	Repository where the file is being imported	path	string	no	
name	Name of the file	query	string	no	

2.2.2.2 Sensor/API Service

This service is a subset of the provided functionalities of the Field Indicator one described in section X.Y.Z, which is utilized also in case of sensor readings.

2.2.2.3 File Handler Service

The File Handler service is responsible for the upload of xls datasets and consists of a single generic endpoint that accepts as input the file along with the pilot which has provided it and outputs a JSON object representation of it based on the headers of the xls. This output follows the format expected by the Rdfization service which is called by the respective Apache Nifi workflow.

The screenshot shows a REST client interface for a POST request to the endpoint `/steps/generic/dataset-upload` with the operation `handleGenericFileUpload`. The parameters section is as follows:

Name	Description
file * required file (formData)	file
<input type="text" value="Choose File"/> NaturalCosm...eSheet.xlsx	
pilot string (query)	pilot
<input type="text" value="symbeeosis"/>	

At the bottom, there is an `Execute` button and a `Clear` button. The `Responses` section shows the `Response content type` set to `application/json;charset=UTF-8`.

Figure 15: The expected input to the file handler service creation endpoint

```
{
  "Antioxidant activity ABTS (µg/mL trolox)": [
    "12.35",
    "12.38"
  ],
  "Sample": [
    "I.A.1_M",
    "I.A.1_U"
  ],
  "Refractive index": [
    "20.47",
    "18.93"
  ],
  "Vineyard Id": [
    "I.A.1",
    "I.A.1"
  ],
  "City": [
    "Aigio",
    "Aigio"
  ],
  "Extraction Method": [
    "Maceration",
    "Ultrasound"
  ],
}
```

Figure 16: A sample output of a call to the File Handler service

2.2.3 Retrieval Layer

This layer is the one responsible for the retrieval of data by accessing the internal storage engines of the BDG stack through the provided API endpoints as described in the previous sections, or by semantic queries done to GraphDB and geospatial ones currently performed through the GEOCLIDEAN service.

2.2.3.1 Knowledge Base Searches

2.2.3.1.1 Saved queries

This controller provides the possibility to save and load commonly used queries. Saved queries can be either shared with other users, or kept private.

[/rest/sparql/saved-queries - GET](#)

Retrieve a list of saved queries.

Table 23: Parameters for retrieval of saved queries

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
name	You can optionally retrieve a specific query by name	query	string	Yes	None (retrieve all queries)
owner	Filter by owner	query	string	Yes	None (no filter)

[/rest/sparql/saved-queries - POST](#)

Create a new saved query.

Table 24: Parameters for creation of new saved query

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
query	Json with query body, name and weather to share it	body	application/json	no	

Sample body

```

{
  "name": "SPARQL Select template",
  "body": "SELECT ?s ?p ?o\nWHERE {\n\t?s ?p ?o .\n} LIMIT 100",
  "shared": false
}

```

Figure 17: A sample of a POST request to /rest/sparql/saved-queries

/rest/sparql/saved-queries - PUT

Edit an existing saved query.

Table 25: Parameters for editing of a saved query

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
query	Json with query body, name and weather to share it	body	application/json	no	

Sample body

```

{
  "name": "SPARQL Select template",
  "body": "SELECT ?s ?p ?o\nWHERE {\n\t?s ?p ?o .\n} LIMIT 100",
  "shared": false
}

```

Figure 18: A sample of a PUT request to the /rest/sparql/saved-queries

/rest/sparql/saved-queries - DELETE

Delete an existing saved query.

Table 26: Parameters for deleting a saved query

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
name	Name of the query that will be deleted	query	string	No	

2.2.3.2 Geospatial Searches

The BDG stack allows for geospatial searches over the provided geographical data for the provided fields. This is currently performed in an abstract way through the GEOCLIDEAN service in which all of the fields that require such analysis are stored in.

The way this is achieved is by providing the parcel id of a specific field, as stored in the GEOCLIDEAN service, and receive as a response the indexes that the service has extracted through satellite image processing, along with bounding geographical information for the specific field.

In the future we plan on integrating more advanced geospatial searches into GraphDB which will allow for such searches in a future release.

2.2.3.3 GraphDB JDBC API

The GraphDB JDBC API allows the use of RDF data by accessing GraphDB through a BI tool of choice (such as Tableau or Microsoft Power BI) as a data scientist or through SQL as an engineer with no experience in SPARQL. This functionality is provided by the JDBC GraphDB driver. This allows users to use SPARQL SELECT queries to create SQL views and access all GraphDB features, including plugins and SPARQL federation. This feature is based on the Apache Calcite protocol and performs optimizations and mapping.

The JDBC driver works with preconfigured SQL views (tables) that are stored under each repository that accesses the data. The SQL View Manager is integrated into the GraphDB Workbench to simplify the table creation process. This allows users to configure, save, update, visualize, and delete SQL views that can be used with the JDBC driver. Each SQL view is based on a SPARQL SELECT query and requires additional metadata to configure the SQL columns.

The JDBC interface is provided as a more user friendly alternative to the SPARQL interface. The JDBC connector provides SQL access over a virtual table.

On the GraphDB side, the virtual tables are configured based on what data needs to be accessible. Users can connect to the JDBC interface with most programming languages. Once connected, users query the data using SQL. The database translates the query to a SPARQL query and based on the predefined configuration returns the up-to-date state of the underlying data.

Comparison between the SPARQL vs the JDBC access:

- The JDBC requires users to know up-front what data they will need to access programmatically.
- The JDBC data transfer will be more performant than most SPARQL results serializations due to their verbosity.
- JDBC/ODBC has support in most programming languages while SPARQL libraries remain limited.
- The JDBC requires SQL experience which is a more common query language.

An example configuration for the interface

```
PREFIX ex:<http://example.com/ex>
PREFIX base:<http://example/base/>
PREFIX rdfs:<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
```

```
select ?restaurant_name ?short_description ?long_description ?calendar where {
  ?s a base:Restaurant;
     rdfs:label ?restaurant_name;
     ex:shortDescription ?short_description;
     ex:longDescription ?long_description;
     ex:calendar ?calendar.
  # !filter
}
```

The data type mapping interface

SQL table configuration ❗

Table name
restaurant_data

Data query | Column types

Column	SQL type	Precision	Is nullable	RDF type for SPARQL FILTER()
calendar	string		<input type="checkbox"/>	http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string
short_description	string		<input type="checkbox"/>	http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string
long_description	string		<input type="checkbox"/>	http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string
restaurant_name	string		<input type="checkbox"/>	http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string

Suggest

Save | Cancel Preview

Based on this configuration we can execute the below SQL query, where nl_restaurants is the GraphDB virtual repository.

Select * from nl_restaurants.restaurant_data

2.2.4 Processing Layer

The processing layer is where the actual processing of the collected data is performed prior or after they are stored in the BDG stack. It is the layer responsible for the rdfization of the provided data, the data stream handling and processing, the geospatial analysis performed and the semantic enrichment. In the following sections we will describe each of the components in more detail.

2.2.4.1 Rdfization Service

In this section we describe the available ways the rdfization of the data can be done for the BDG stack. To facilitate this process 2 tools are provided, a command line one, namely TARQL, and a service with API endpoints.

2.2.4.1.1 TARQL

TARQL (Tabular SPARQL) is a command-line tool for converting CSV files to RDF using SPARQL 1.1 syntax. It's written in Java and based on Apache ARQ. CSV file's contents are input into the query as a table of bindings. This allows manipulation of CSV data using the full power of SPARQL 1.1 syntax, and in particular the generation of RDF using CONSTRUCT queries.

TARQL is particularly useful as it is lightweight, efficient and works in streaming mode. It also allows us to define the transformation in 100% declarative fashion.

For the shared vocabulary, such as the variables of the different observations and, various coded lists we set up several public google sheet tables that contain the master source data.

- [BDG Coded lists](#)¹ Contains all used coded lists
- [BDG Variable](#)² Contains Measures, Dimensions and Variables

We use the chart tools data source protocol to convert them to CSV and serve them over HTTP. The syntax is as follows:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/{{DOC_ID}}/gviz/tq?tqx=out:csv&gid={{SHEET_ID}} where DOC_ID and SHEET_ID are both available from the sheet's URL.

For example, the grapeVariety sheet has:

DOC_ID=19fdrdisQqihUN68_Ib-VEGVgxxEock-IldDWUPfVUMA and
sheet=grapeVariety

Then we use the tarql queries to construct the turtle files containing the rdfized data.

Example TARQL query producing Measurement variables:

```
CONSTRUCT {
  ?URI a qb:MeasureProperty, sosa:ObservableProperty, ?CODED_PROP_TYPE;
      rdfs:label      ?label ;
      rdfs:comment    ?description ;
      sdmx-attribute:unitMeasure ?UNIT ;
      sosa:hasFeatureOfInterest ?FEATURE ;
      bdg:measurementContext ?MEASUREMENT_CONTEXT ;
      bdg:derivedFrom      ?DERIVED_FROM ;
      bdg:statisticalSummary ?STATSUM ;
      qb:codeList          ?CODEDLIST ;
      qb:concept           sdmx-concept:obsValue ;
      rdfs:range           ?CODEDCLASS ;
      ?EXTRA_P             ?EXTRA_O ;
      .
}
WHERE
{
  bind(1+"" as ?UNDEF)
  bind(uri(concat(str(bdg:),?uri)) as ?URI)
  bind(uri(tarql:expandPrefixedName(?unitMeasure)) as ?UNIT)
  bind(uri(concat("feature/",?featureOfInterest)) as ?FEATURE)
  bind(uri(?measurementContext) as ?MEASUREMENT_CONTEXT)
  bind(uri(concat("statisticalSummary/",?statisticalSummary)) as ?STATSUM)
  bind(uri(if(bound(?codedList),qb:CodedProperty,?codedList)) as ?CODED_PROP_TYPE)
  bind(uri(?codedList) as ?CODEDLIST)
  bind(uri(concat(str(bdg:),ucase(substr(?codedList,1,1)),substr(?codedList,2))) as ?CODEDCLASS)
}
```

```

bind(uri(tarql:expandPrefixedName(?extra_p)) as ?EXTRA_P)
bind(if(bound(?extra_o),uri(?extra_o),if(bound(?extra_o_str),?extra_o_str,?UNDEF)) as ?EXTRA_O)
bind(coalesce(?derivedFrom,"") as ?derivedFromNotNull)
?derivedFrom_split apf:strSplit (?derivedFromNotNull ",")
bind(if(bound(?derivedFrom),uri(concat(str(bdg:),?derivedFrom_split)),?UNDEF) as ?DERIVED_FROM)
}

```

Figure 19: Example TARQL query

Provided the following input line concerning the observation of Soil Electrical Conductivity, at 0.5m separation

Table 27: Soil Elastic Conductivity measures

uri	label	unitMeasure	codedList	featureOfInterest	measurementContext
CV05m	Soil Electrical Conductivity, separation 0.5m	bdg-unit:Milli-S-PER-M		Soil	feature/Soil/separation-50cm

The service will produce the following bit of RDF.

```

bdg:CV05m rdf:type qb:MeasureProperty ;
rdf:type sosa:ObservableProperty ;
rdfs:label "Soil Electric Conductivity, separation 0.5m" ;
sdmx-attribute:unitMeasure bdg-unit:Milli-S-PER-M ;
sosa:hasFeatureOfInterest <http://data.bigdatagrapes.eu/resource/feature/Soil> ;
bdg:measurementContext <http://data.bigdatagrapes.eu/resource/feature/Soil/separation-0.5m> ;
qb:concept sdmx-concept:obsValue .

```

Figure 20: Sample RDF produced by TARQL

2.2.4.1.2 Rdfization API

The rdfization API is an endpoint implemented to make the rdfization process possible also through HTTP requests, following the microservice architecture. Its responsibility is similar to the TARQL's described in the previous section.

It consists of endpoints handling POST requests for each of the pilot's datasets. It is a service built with Java and Spring Boot, utilizing a library called [RDFBeans](#) that provides the capability of annotating a Java Class with attributes used for generating valid RDF classes. Each request done to its endpoints generates a valid RDF/XML file available for download while also posting data to BDG's GraphDB instance for the semantic enrichment and linking to happen.

```
[
  {
    "Antioxidant activity ABTS (µg/mL trolox)": 0,
    "Antioxidant activity DPPH (µg/mL trolox)": 0,
    "City": "string",
    "Extraction Method": "string",
    "Parcel ID": "string",
    "Refractive index": 0,
    "Region": "string",
    "Sample": "string",
    "Sample collection day": "2019-06-24T09:00:46.110Z",
    "Total flavonoid content, TFC (µg/mL quercetin)": 0,
    "Total microbial count": "string",
    "Total phenolic content, TPC (µg/mL gallic acid)": 0,
    "Variety": "string",
    "Vineyard": "string",
    "Vineyard Id": "string",
    "Yeasts and moulds": "string",
    "pH": 0
  }
]
```

Figure 21: Expected JSON schema for Symbeosis data

```
-<rdf:Description rdf:about="http://dev.bigdatagrapes.eu/data/cosmetics/T101">
  <rdf:type rdf:resource="http://purl.org/linked-data/cube#Observation"/>
  <grapeVariety rdf:resource="http://dev.bigdatagrapes.eu/grapeVariety/Agiorgitiko"/>
  <antioxidantActivityDPPHTrolox rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double">4.31</antioxidantActivityDPPHTrolox>
  <dataSet rdf:resource="http://dev.bigdatagrapes.eu/data/cosmetics"/>
  <tfcQuercetin rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double">12.24</tfcQuercetin>
  <totalMicrobialCount rdf:resource="http://dev.bigdatagrapes.eu/microbialCount/LT10"/>
  <date rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime">2018-05-08T02:00:00.000+02:00</date>
  <pH rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double">5.89</pH>
  <tpcGallicAcid rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double">5.96</tpcGallicAcid>
  <yeastsAndMoulds rdf:resource="http://dev.bigdatagrapes.eu/microbialCount/LT10"/>
  <refractiveIndex rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double">18.93</refractiveIndex>
  <antioxidantActivityABSTrolox rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double">12.38</antioxidantActivityABSTrolox>
</rdf:Description>
```

Figure 22: Sample RDF/XML created with Rdfization API

Figure 21 shows the JSON schema requests for the Symbeosis pilot should follow and figure 22 shows a sample of the respective RDF/XML file generated.

In terms of input/output, the endpoints of this service expect a JSON object in the body of the requests and produce an application/rdf+xml response. Each request sent to this service is also logged into MySQL. The schema of this stored information has the JSON object that was sent, the timestamp it was first sent, the file that was generated and whether or not the upload into GraphDB was successful. This is done for optimization purposes in case the same request is sent multiple times and to be able to keep track of failed imports at GraphDB so that they can be repeated using offline Apache Nifi workflows. The source code is available [here](#).

2.2.4.2 Geospatial Analysis Service

The geospatial analysis for the BDG stack is currently performed by the GEOCLIDEAN service. In this service, the information on the outcomes of the satellite image processing workflows have been stored and are available for queries through the respective service.

More specifically, 8 different parameters are monitored, analyzed and provided upon request to the response of the service. Table 28 shows a quick overview of these parameters.

Table 28: Parameters monitored by GEOCLEDIAN service

Name	Description	Sample
NDVI	<p>Vegetation vitality. NDVI correlates with the amount of leaf area (LAI) of active, healthy, green vegetation. Advantage: The most widely used vegetation index. Disadvantage: It saturates at high LAI levels and therefore shows limited variation in dense fields with high biomass. It minimizes topographic effects.</p> <p>Negative values of NDVI (values approaching -1) typically correspond to open water. Values around zero (-0.1 to 0.1) generally correspond to bare soil, barren areas of rock, sand, or snow. Low, positive values represent low or sparse vegetation (approximately 0.2 to 0.4), while high values indicate dense vegetation (values approaching 1).</p> <p>Native resolution: 10m</p>	
NDRE1	<p>The Red Edge Indices are designed to estimate chlorophyll content in the canopy. More sensitivity in vegetation with high LAI. Less sensitivity to open water. There are several different formulas for the NDRE index. We selected the most appropriate ones.</p> <p>Native resolution: 20m</p>	

<p>NDRE2</p>	<p>The Red Edge Indices are designed to estimate chlorophyll content in the canopy. More sensitivity in vegetation with high LAI. Less sensitivity to open water. There are several different formulas for the NDRE index. We selected the most appropriate ones.</p> <p>Native resolution: 20m</p>	
<p>NDWI</p>	<p>Sensitive to Vegetation water content & water stress. Allows drought monitoring. NDWI is less sensitive to atmospheric effects than NDVI. Attention: There are also other "NDWI" indexes with different meaning.</p> <p>Native resolution: 20m</p>	
<p>SAVI</p>	<p>Reduced soil background effects. SAVI tries to correct for bare soil areas in the field. Therefore, it is interesting in sparse vegetation canopies or early growing stages.</p> <p>Native resolution: 20m</p>	

<p>EVI2</p>	<p>More sensitivity in the late growth stage (high LAI). It tries to correct for soil background signals and atmospheric influences.</p> <p>Native resolution: 20m</p>	
<p>CI-RE</p>	<p>Very high Chlorophyll & Nitrogen sensitivity. Canopy Chlorophyll & Nitrogen contents can be derived for a wide range of crops (e.g. potato, soybean, maize) and grassland. This can be used to plan harvests.</p> <p>Native resolution: 20m</p>	
<p>NPCRI</p>	<p>Associated with chlorophyll and nitrogen content. This index can be found in precision agriculture applications. Crops with a low Nitrogen content can have a high carotenoid to chlorophyll ratio. Using the red and blue spectral bands, NPCRI captures the information needed to quantify chlorophyll and Nitrogen.</p> <p>Native resolution: 10m</p>	

All of the outcomes of this analysis are available either in PNG, KML or GEOTIFF format and the attribute information is available in JSON.

2.2.4.3 Stream Processing Engine

The stream processing service is the one responsible with collecting and processing data that show high velocity in real-time. It is currently employed for data that are generated using sensors deployed in the field. Figure 23 shows an overview of this service, along with the components used.

Figure 23: An overview of the stream processing engine

As depicted in the figure above the stream processing engine is based on Apache Kafka. On the one side there are dedicated Kafka Producers that collect data from API endpoints, batch sensor data or files that are stored into Kafka topics. Any processing required on the stream is done using Kafka streams, the output of which is stored into different topics. Depending on the workflow required by each the data can be sent to the geo annotation service, currently able to identify countries and continents by providing cities, the ontology annotation service where based on selected ontologies (eg. Agrovoc or Foodvoc) terms are extracted and finally to the Rdfization service for the RDF data to be generated and inserted into GraphDB. All of the processed data is also sent for its intermediate storage to Apache Cassandra, taking advantage of the high write throughput it has.

2.2.4.4 Semantic Annotation of Large Unstructured Documents

2.2.4.4.1 Concept Extraction Service

The Concept Extraction Service (CES) is a GATE application wrapper, that allows you to convert any GATE application into a scalable web service. It has a default GATE pipeline for concept extraction, but can also work with custom GATE pipelines.

The concept extraction pipeline retrieves from text various types of entities and relations. The extraction is based on gazetteers and a combination of rule-based and machine learning techniques. We apply word sense disambiguation techniques and attach to each extracted entity or relation a unique URI pointing to its corresponding concept in the knowledge base. It uses a gazetteer that is generated and continuously updated using a custom SPARQL query.

Semantic Annotation Solution - the Process of Building It

Figure 24: Overview of the semantic annotation solution

There is one main endpoint that is used for annotation of unstructured documents:

/extract - POST

Table 29: Parameters for document annotation service

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
document	Text that will be semantically annotated	body	text/plain , text/xml , text/html	no	

timeout	Max execution time	query	long	yes	None
---------	--------------------	-------	------	-----	------

2.2.5 Management Layer

There are two controllers that are used for managing the graph database. The first one is responsible for the security management - it is responsible for administering users and their rights with respect to the data. The second is for administering the data locations and switching between remote repositories.

2.2.5.0.1 Security

[/rest/security - GET](#)

Check if security is enabled - returns true/false.

[/rest/security - POST](#)

Enable or disable security

Table 30: Parameters for repository security enabling

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
useSecurity	New security setting	body	boolean	no	

[/rest/security/freeaccess - GET](#)

Get free access configuration

Sample response:

```

{
  "enabled": false,
  "authorities": [],
  "appSettings": {
    "DEFAULT_INFERENCE": true,
    "DEFAULT_SAMEAS": true,
    "IGNORE_SHARED_QUERIES": false,
    "EXECUTE_COUNT": true
  }
}

```

Figure 25: Sample response of the /rest/security/freeaccess - GET request

/rest/security/freeaccess - POST

Change free access configuration.

Table 31: Parameters for configuration of free access

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
freeaccess	Free access configuration	body	application/json	no	

Sample body:

```
{
  "enabled": false,
  "authorities": [],
  "appSettings": {
    "DEFAULT_INFERENCE": true,
    "DEFAULT_SAMEAS": true,
    "IGNORE_SHARED_QUERIES": false,
    "EXECUTE_COUNT": true
  }
}
```

Figure 26: Sample body of a POST request to /rest/security/freeaccess

/rest/security/overrideauth - GET

Get authentication override configuration.

Sample response:

```

    {
      "enabled": false,
      "authorities": [
        "ROLE_USER",
        "ROLE_MONITORING",
        "ROLE_REPO_MANAGER"
      ],
      "appSettings": {
        "DEFAULT_INFERENCE": "true",
        "DEFAULT_SAMEAS": "true",
        "IGNORE_SHARED_QUERIES": "false",
        "EXECUTE_COUNT": "true"
      }
    }
  }

```

Figure 27: Sample response of a call to /rest/security/overrideauth

[/rest/security/user - GET](#)

Get a list of all users and their rights and settings.

Sample response:

```

    [
      {
        "username": "admin",
        "password": "",
        "grantedAuthorities": [
          "ROLE_ADMIN"
        ],
        "appSettings": {
          "DEFAULT_INFERENCE": true,
          "DEFAULT_SAMEAS": true,
          "IGNORE_SHARED_QUERIES": false,
          "EXECUTE_COUNT": true
        },
        "dateCreated": 1556102735624
      }
    ]

```

Figure 28: Sample response of a call to /rest/security/user

[/rest/security/user/{username} - GET](#)

Retrieve configuration for a given user.

Table 32: Parameters for retrieval of configuration for a user

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
username	User for which configuration will be retrieved	path	string	no	

Sample response:

```

{
  username: "admin",
  password: "",
  grantedAuthorities: [
    "ROLE_ADMIN"
  ],
  appSettings: {
    DEFAULT_INFERENCE: true,
    DEFAULT_SAMEAS: true,
    IGNORE_SHARED_QUERIES: false,
    EXECUTE_COUNT: true
  },
  dateCreated: 1556102735624
}

```

Figure 29: Sample response of a request to /rest/security/user/{username} - GET endpoint

/rest/security/user/{username} - POST

For creating new users.

Table 33: Parameters for creation of new users

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
username	New user username	path	string	no	
user	New user configuration	body	application/json	no	
X-GraphDB-Password	GraphDB password	header	string	no	

Sample body:

```

{
  "appSettings": {},
  "dateCreated": "2019-06-18T11:22:07.185Z",
  "grantedAuthorities": ["ROLE_USER"],
  "password": "string",
  "username": "user"
}

```

Figure 30: Sample response of a request to /rest/security/user/{username} - POST endpoint

/rest/security/user/{username} - PUT

For editing user configurations

Table 34: Parameters for changing user profile and access

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
username	Username for which configuration will be edited	path	string	no	
user	New user configuration	body	application/json	no	
X-GraphDB-Password	GraphDB password	header	string	no	

2.2.5.0.2 Location

/rest/locations - GET

Get a list of all connected GraphDB locations.

Sample response:

```

[
  {
    "uri": "",
    "label": "Local",
    "username": null,
    "password": null,
    "active": true,
    "local": true,
    "system": true,
    "errorMsg": null,
    "defaultRepository": null
  }
]

```

Figure 31: Sample response of a request to /rest/locations - GET endpoint

/rest/locations - POST

Edit settings for an already connected location.

Table 35: Parameters for configuration of a connected location

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
location	JSON with the new location settings	body	application/json	no	

Sample body:

```

{
  "active": false,
  "defaultRepository": "string",
  "errorMsg": "string",
  "label": "string",
  "local": true,
  "password": "string",
  "system": false,
  "uri": "",
  "username": "string"
}

```

Figure 32: Sample response of a request to /rest/locations - POST endpoint

/rest/locations - PUT

Connect to a new GraphDB location

Table 36: Parameters for new GraphDB location

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
location	JSON with the new location	body	application/json	no	

Sample body:

```
{
  "active": false,
  "defaultRepository": "string",
  "errorMsg": "string",
  "label": "string",
  "local": true,
  "password": "string",
  "system": false,
  "uri": "",
  "username": "string"
}
```

Figure 33: Sample response of a request to /rest/locations - PUT endpoint

/rest/locations - DELETE

Disconnect a specified location

Table 37: Parameters for disconnecting a location

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
uri	GraphDB location URL	query	string	no	

/rest/security/user/{username} - DELETE

Table 38: Parameters for deletion of a user profile

Parameter	Description	Parameter type	Data Type	Optional	Default
username	User for which	path	string	no	

	configuration will be retrieved				
X-GraphDB-Password	GraphDB password	header	string	no	

2.2.5.1 Metadata Service

The metadata service is the one responsible for the storage of metadata information on pilots and service of the BDG platform. It is one of the core services in the stack since all the workflows that occur inside the stack query its endpoints to get information on the steps and the respective services that need to be queried.

It currently consists of 2 endpoints handling PUT requests and another 2 handling GET requests. The first 2 are for the creation or update on metadata information stored either for a pilot or for a specific service, while the GET endpoints are the ones where one can search for stored information by providing filters based on the selected model.

Table 39 shows the parameters expected by the endpoint that handles storage of pilot metadata.

Table 39: Parameters for description of Pilots metadata

Parameter	Description	Required
ID	The ID of the pilot metadata object to be created or updated. In case it is not existent, the service will automatically assign a new, if existent the service will create it with the supplied one, which if already present in the storage engine an update of the values with the provided will happen.	no
name	The name of the pilot	yes
parcelIds	The parcel ids of the fields the pilot has provided. This provides the linking to the GEOCLIDEAN's service.	no
competenceQuestions	A list of competence questions as set by the pilot. This field provides the ability to automate the BDG stack validation process.	no

Figure 34 shows the JSON schema as expected by this endpoint.

```

{
  "competenceQuestions": [
    "string"
  ],
  "id": "string",
  "name": "string",
  "parcelIds": [
    0
  ]
}

```

Figure 34: The JSON schema expected by the Metadata service

The expected parameters for the service metadata endpoint are as shown in Table 40.

Table 40: Metadata service parameters

Parameter	Description	Required
name	The name of the service	yes
model	A Java (or python) class that the data model of this service follows. This exists so that the automation of the service calls can be made easier.	no
endpoint	The URL in which the service is.	yes
inputFormat	The expected input format of the service.	yes
outputFormat	The output format of the specific service.	yes
responseFormat	A Java (or python) class the response of the specific service follows.	no

Figure 35 shows the JSON representation of the expected input of this endpoint.

```
{
  "endpoint": "string",
  "inputFormat": "string",
  "model": "string",
  "name": "string",
  "outputFormat": "string",
  "responseFormat": "string"
}
```

Figure 35: The JSON schema expected by the Service Metadata endpoint

This service is implemented using Spring Boot and Java and all of the data are stored in MongoDB.

2.2.6 Support Layer

This layer is where the tools and components that provide the intelligence of the stack are stored and accessed. It consists of models and libraries that attempt to use the provided datasets in order to cover the desired outcomes as described by the pilots. In the following sections we describe the current state of this layer in terms of the completed and integrated components.

2.2.6.1 Correlation Service

The correlation service is a wrapper API built on top of the correlation scripts to provide access following the microservice architecture principles. It is a python application built with Flask that utilizes the python libraries pandas and numpy for the data exploration and analysis.

The service has different endpoints for each of the different correlations that will be performed in the context of BDG. It expects the input files that each correlation expects to have in the respective format.

In terms of the requests made to it, they are GET requests in which only the pilot and the correlation work need to be passed as path parameters to the URL. The response of this service is a zip file that contains the produced correlation histograms.

2.2.6.2 Predictive Analytics Service

The Predictive Analytics Service implements the data preprocessing, model training and inference mechanisms for machine-learned solutions supporting decision making activities of the stakeholders. These functionalities are provided by an evolving portfolio of machine-learning algorithms tailored to the specific user-provided test cases.

A predictive analytics methods is any mechanisms, technique or algorithm that puts into operation the data preprocessing (i.e., data filtering, data cleaning, feature engineering), model training (i.e., classification and regression machine-learned models trained on the provided preprocessed data to generate software artifacts to be deployed at inference time) and model inference (i.e., usage of trained models to perform predictions on new data). The BigDataGrapes predictive analytics service thus provides three general abstract task types: *preprocess*, *train* and *fit*.

A *preprocess* task is any task that takes as input structured or unstructured data from the Persistence and/or Ingestion layers and applies transformations to the data before feeding it to a *train* task, producing an output stored into the Persistence layer. Typically, whenever the data is collected from heterogeneous sources, it is

gathered in a raw format which is not feasible for directly training a machine learning model. Examples of *preprocess* task implementations include data structures and algorithms to rescale data to specific value intervals, to binarize data transforming all values above the threshold to 1 and all equal to or below to 0, normalize the data transforming attributes with a Gaussian distribution and differing means and standard deviations to a standard Gaussian distribution with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1.

A *train* task takes as input a suitable preprocessed data set and executed implementation-specific algorithms to produce a machine-learned model. The output model implementation will depend on the structure of the training data and will be stored for reuse in the Persistence layer. A *train* task can perform multiple sub-activities such as parameter fitting, grid search analysis, parameter sweeping, model compression, etc.

A *fit* task takes a trained model and a preprocessed dataset from the Persistence layer, and applies the trained model to the instances provided in the preprocessed dataset.

In the following tables, we detail the service APIs of the predictive analytics service.

Table 41: Predictive analytics service parameters - Data Pre-processing

Operation	preprocessData
Interaction	Persistence Layer -> Support Layer -> Persistence Layer (synchronous)
Description	Given an input dataset identifier, an output dataset identifier, and optionally some implementation-dependent configuration parameters, launch the <i>preprocess</i> task that applies data transformations and return a status identifier.
Input	inputDatasetId: persistenceDataId outputDatasetId: persistenceDataId config: KeyValueCollection [0,1]
Output	status: done, decline, fail msg: String [0,1]
Pre-conditions	inputDatasetId is well-formed and the referenced dataset exists outputDatasetId is well-formed and the referenced dataset doesn't exist config, if not null, is well-formed
Post-conditions	status = done: a preprocess activity has been executed and terminated with success, the output dataset is created, msg if null status = decline: at least one of the pre-conditions is not fulfilled; no preprocess task is started, the output dataset is not created, msg documents the pre-condition violations
Exceptions	status = fail: the task is unable to carry out the operation because of internal failure, the output dataset is not created, msg, if not null, documents the internal failure causes.

Table 42: Predictive analytics service parameters - Training

Operation	trainModel
-----------	-------------------

Interaction	Persistence Layer -> Support Layer -> Persistence Layer (synchronous)
Description	Given an input dataset identifier, an output model identifier, and optionally some implementation-dependent configuration parameters, launch the <i>train</i> task that takes as input the preprocessed dataset and generates an implementation-specific model representation on disk.
Input	inputDatasetId: persistenceDataId outputModelId: persistenceModelId config: KeyValueTypeMap [0,1]
Output	status: done, decline, fail msg: String [0,1]
Pre-conditions	inputDatasetId is well-formed and the referenced dataset exists outputModelId is well-formed and the referenced model doesn't exist config, if not null, is well-formed
Post-conditions	status = done: a train activity has been executed and terminated with success, the output model is created, msg is null status = decline: at least one of the pre-conditions is not fulfilled; no train task is started, the output model is not created, msg documents the pre-condition violations
Exceptions	status = fail: the task is unable to carry out the operation because of internal failure, the output model is not created, msg, if not null, documents the internal failure causes.

Table 43: Predictive analytics service parameters - FitData

Operation	fitData
Interaction	Persistence Layer -> Support Layer -> Persistence Layer (synchronous)
Description	Given an input dataset identifier, a input model identifier, a output result identifier, and optionally some implementation-dependent configuration parameters, launch the <i>fit</i> task that performs inference on the input data using the specified model and storing the results in the output dataset.
Input	inputDatasetId: persistenceDataId inputModelId: persistenceModelId outputDataId: persistenceDataId config: KeyValueTypeMap [0,1]
Output	status: done, decline, w fails msg: String [0,1]
Pre-conditions	inputDatasetId is well-formed and the referenced dataset exists inputModelId is well-formed and the referenced model exists outputDataId is well-formed and the references data doesn't exist config, if not null, is well-formed
Post-conditions	status = done: an inference activity has been executed and terminated with success, the

	output data is created, msg in null status = decline: at least one of the pre-conditions is not fulfilled; no fit task is started, the output data is not created, msg documents the pre-condition violations
Exceptions	status = fail: the task is unable to carry out the operation because of internal failure, the output data is not created, msg, if not null, documents the internal failure causes.

2.2.7 Visualization Layer

The visualisation layer provides various means to explore and interact with data for end-users. The benefits of visualising complex data arise from being able to better interact and understand data by aggregating, filtering, searching or scaling down relevant information. Thus, a large volume of data with potentially complex information becomes more easily consumable. Dashboards, for example, are particularly useful for providing a quick and easy access to diverse visual components which allow further explorations of data. In the past, we have proposed and showcased a number of visualisations for the project including interactive visual analytic components (5.1), uncertainty-aware visualisations (5.2) and trust-aware DSS (5.3). An overview of these components is shown below:

Figure 36: Interactive visual analytic components and visualisation selector

Figure 37: Uncertainty-aware visualisations

Figure 38: Trust-aware decision support system

Through a series of discussions with pilot partners in the past months, we have defined visualisation requirements for individual pilot partners. We discovered that while each pilot collects/measures slightly different data from one another, some shared certain areas of interest which means more than one pilot partner can potentially benefit from the same type of visualisations. For instance, both AUA and INRAE require a correlation tool to explore and filter the variables for optimum prediction scenarios. At the time of writing this report, we have developed a total of 6 complete visualisation dashboards across 5 pilot partners and evaluated their usability, among other metrics. Detailed descriptions of each visualisation and pilot requirements can be

found in the latest version of D8.5 (Evaluation Report and KPI Assessment). Below is an overview of these visualisations:

Figure 39: Pilot 1: Visualisation developed for the correlation task of the table and wine grape pilot: <http://picasso.experiments.cs.kuleuven.be:3603/>

Figure 40: Pilot 2: Visualisation developed for the leaf counting task of the winemaking pilot: <http://picasso.experiments.cs.kuleuven.be:3327/>

INRAE - De la Vigne au Vin
Vins Rouges et Blancs

Figure 41: Pilot 2: Visualisation developed for the correlation task of the winemaking pilot: <http://picasso.experiments.cs.kuleuven.be:3602/>

Figure 42: Pilot 2: Visualisation developed for the vine to wine exploration task of the winemaking pilot: <http://picasso.experiments.cs.kuleuven.be:3333/>

Figure 43: Pilot 3: Visualisation developed for the irrigation task of the farm management pilot: <http://picasso.experiments.cs.kuleuven.be:3328/>

Pilot 4: Visualisation developed for the bio-efficacy correlation task of the natural cosmetics pilot: <http://picasso.experiments.cs.kuleuven.be:3620/>

Figure 44: Pilot 5: Visualisation developed for the price prediction task of the food protection pilot:
<http://picasso.experiments.cs.kuleuven.be:3541/>

3 BigDataGrapes Platform Monitoring

Using the Big Data Software stack you may **build a very robust data platform instance**; capable of **handling huge amounts of data; harmonising, linking together and enhancing** in any ML/DL or any other possible way available. However, **what if**:

- a node in your [Elasticsearch](#) instance stops working?
- your [MongoDB](#) deployment consumes too much memory?
- the awesome model you have designed and implemented takes up too much CPU/GPU?
- the [Apache Airflow](#) webserver and/or scheduler stops working?

Depending on your setup there are many more questions where that came from but you get the point.

3.1 ENSURE UPTIME FOR EVERY COMPONENT DEPLOYED TO THE STACK

How to ensure uptime in data platforms? To this crucial question all we can answer is based on our experience building and maintaining a data platform handling almost a billion data records with different types.

Our infrastructure is a **microservice** one. This means that every single piece of component is wrapped up with a **bunch of API endpoints**, accessible through various **ports** in our **servers**.

Every newly deployed project, API service, storage engine in the infrastructure should come with a check-up script. This means that each and every time a new framework, tool, storage engine, project is deployed the following script is also setup as a **cronjob**.

```
#!/bin/bash

nmap -p 9200 localhost | grep "closed" > temp.tmp

lines="$(cat temp.tmp | wc -l)"

if [ ${lines} -eq 1 ];
then
    lines="$(tail -n 50 {path_to_logfile})"
    sendmail -f {from_mail_address} -t {to_mail_address} -u {subject} -m
{mail_content} -s {smtp_server} -xu {username} -xp {password}
    sudo service elasticsearch stop
    sudo sh -c "echo 3 > /proc/sys/vm/drop_caches"
    sudo service elasticsearch start
fi
```

In this script we are checking for the uptime of an **Elasticsearch** instance running at port 9200:

- we are using the command line tool **nmap** to check for the availability of the port,
- if found to be closed an email containing the last 50 lines of the respective service's log is sent to a selected mail account,
- the service is stopped (should it not be already),
- the system's cache is cleared, and
- the service is restarted.

And such script can be executed every 2 minutes within our architecture for every single component deployed.

3.2 NOT ALL PROBLEMS COME FROM THE INFRASTRUCTURE

Many problems may come from the implementation and wrap-up code. One has to ensure that such cases are also monitored. Thankfully, **Elastic** has made available tools to that end. **APM** is out there and easily integratable. Let's dive into a specific example of such integration into a Spring Data project.

First one has to download and install/run an APM server instance:

- head over to <https://www.elastic.co/downloads/apm> and get the latest version available,
- untar the file,
- edit the **apm-server.yml** file and set the desired configuration parameters,
- in this example we will set the port,
- the connection to our monitoring dedicated Elasticsearch instance, and
- the connection to the respective Kibana instance for visualization purposes,
- execute the respective binary.

```
##### APM Server Configuration #####
##### APM Server #####

apm-server:
  # Defines the host and port the server is listening on. Use "unix:/path/to.sock"
  # to listen on a unix domain socket.
  host: "{APM_SERVER_IP}:{APM_SERVER_PORT}"

  kibana:
    # For APM Agent configuration in Kibana, enabled must be true.
    enabled: true
    host: "http://{KIBANA_IP}:{KIBANA_PORT}"

#===== Outputs =====
# Configure the output to use when sending the data collected by apm-server.
#----- Elasticsearch output -----
```

```
output.elasticsearch:
  hosts: ["{ELASTICSEARCH_IP}:{ELASTICSEARCH_PORT}"]
```

Now our **APM server** is up and running! Let's connect our Spring Data project to start sending over data. To do that we should:

- include the required dependencies in our project,

```
<dependencies>
  <dependency>
    <groupId>co.elastic.apm</groupId>
    <artifactId>apm-agent-api</artifactId>
    <version>1.11.0</version>
  </dependency>
  <dependency>
    <groupId>co.elastic.apm</groupId>
    <artifactId>apm-agent-attach</artifactId>
    <version>1.11.0</version>
  </dependency>
</dependencies>
```

- create a properties file with the connection parameters,

```
service_name={OUR_SERVICE_IDENTIFIER}
application_packages={PACKAGES}
server_urls=http://{APM_SERVER_IP}:{APM_SERVER_PORT}
capture_body=all
```

- attach the ElasticAPM to our project.

```
public static void main(String[] args) {
    ElasticApmAttacher.attach();
    SpringApplication.run(SearchAPI.class, args);
}
```

Another step is left and we are ready to investigate possible performance issues. This last step applies only to setups involving Tomcat. One needs to link Elastic APM's jar file to her **Tomcat** installation as an environmental variable. To do this, one has to edit the `setenv.sh` file located in the `bin` directory of Tomcat's extraction directory.

```
export CATALINA_OPTS="$CATALINA_OPTS -javaagent:{DIRECTORY_TO_JAR}/elastic-apm-agent-1.11.0.jar"
```

Perfect, if everything was setup correctly it is time to visualize and investigate the results! And what better place to do so other than our **dedicated Kibana instance!**

And this is the highest possible analysis present. You can dive in way deeper even to a method level.

Using such a framework, we have been able to identify where our code has some problems or takes a lot of time to actually execute and focus our work.

4 BigDataGrapes Platform Best Practices

4.1 SETTING UP AN INSTANCE OF THE BIG DATA PLATFORM

All the necessary components to set up an instance of the Big Data Platform are available in the projects Docker hub and can be deployed easily at any infrastructure. The use of dockers is straightforward so in this section, we are describing how one can set up and deploy an instance of the Big Data Platform for a specific use case: collecting and processing food safety incidents that are announced by National Authorities all around the world.

In this case we need to **crawl** and **scrape** various data sources announcing **food recalls** and **border rejections** worldwide. This data may come in various formats; just to give a quick overview: multilingual PDF files, custom formatted Excel files, RSS feeds and of course HTML pages.

How to crawl these data? You can use a tool like the [Crawler4J](#), but we need to customize it a bit in order to cover our needs. Thankfully it's an open source project so that was easy. Currently all it needs is a **yml configuration file** and it takes care of the rest.

```
seeds:
  - https://www.inspection.gc.ca/food-recall-warnings-and-allergy-alerts/eng/1351519587174/1351519588221
  #these are connected through OR
patterns:
  - inspection.gc.ca/about-the-cfia/newsroom/food-recall-warnings/complete-listing
  - inspection.gc.ca/food-recall-warnings-and-allergy-alerts/

neg_patterns:
  - complete-listing/eng/
  - ay=
  - print=

#these are connected through AND
stored:
  - inspection.gc.ca/food-recall-warnings-and-allergy-alerts/

output:
  action: mongo
  belongs: cfia
```

Figure 45:: A (canadian) example of the YML configuration expected by our crawlers

Ok, we got the data, but we need to store it. We have a wide variety of data, each with its own properties. Data concerning food recalls that have a velocity of at most under a hundred per day and data coming from sensors deployed on a field level which presented a velocity of thousands per day; no one framework would be able to meet our needs. So we decided to split the data based on its velocity. Those presenting lower velocity (eg. raw html, xls) would be stored into a [MongoDB](#) instance and those with a higher one into an [Apache Cassandra](#) cluster.

But data is useless if you cannot process it, so the next part of our stack is our **Transformer** into our internal schema; of course based on the entity type we are processing. To that end, we employed into our stack python and PHP scripts as well as a custom Java project, all of which take care of the harmonisation of the collected data.

The next step is how to identify important terms in the collected data like the ingredient that was recalled, the reason behind a recall or the company involved in it. This is where data mining, NLP, NER, ML and DL techniques are employed. A number of projects and respective API endpoints are deployed taking care of this tasks. As far as technologies and frameworks are concerned, we have **Spring {Boot, Data}** projects, **Flask** endpoints taking advantage of **scikit** and **Keras** classifiers all communicating with **Elasticsearch** instances and internally trained models. Each producing an accuracy score, that if above a threshold is accepted as valid response.

Figure: State of the data platform entities as taken from our internal Kibana dashboard instance

The collected data is now harmonised and enriched. If we want to enable human curation we can store the data into an internal CMS (**Drupal**, CKAN, DKAN) in order for it to be easily accessible by our internal food expert team to review, correct and approve for publishing.

And the collected, automatically enriched and human curated data are ready to be published over to our production instances of **Elasticsearch**, ready to be queried by our custom developed **Smart Search API**, visualized over to our application layer.

Such an instance of the Big Data Platform, includes:

- **131 different API endpoints** wrapped on top of each component of the stack;
- over the past year, **14.809.924 requests** have been served by our endpoints;
- with an average response time of **200ms**;
- **9 Elasticsearch** instances;
- **2 Apache Cassandra** nodes;
- **1 MongoDB**;
- **3 Graph Databases** (2 [Neo4j](#) instances and 1 [GraphDB](#)).

All of the above stats were generated by the [Elastic Stack](#), dedicated to monitoring our whole infrastructure.

4.2 ID ASSIGNMENT IN BIG DATA PROJECTS

Using the Big Data Software stack developed in the context of BigDataGrapes you may build (Big) Data Platform instances. One very important aspect that you need to take into consideration is **“How to assign IDs at records in the Data Platform?”**

Now let’s take a step back; this may seem like a trivial task for those out there dealing with relational DBs or rather traditional architectures and platforms. A simple **object = new Object()** or **findById** may suffice.

- But what about complex platforms?
- Data platforms receiving data from various sources?
- Data stored in any kind of storage engines or scraped one-off from another platform?

How can one be certain that everything will be correctly matched throughout a pipeline? The answer is that **special care should be taken as far as id assignment is concerned.**

Many practises may be applied to tackle this problem:

- applying a **hash function** over crawled/scraped urls,
- some kind of **internal identification** process,
- attempting to **identify/extract each source’s unique identification** method (everyone has one!).

Let’s review each of the above.

Hash function over crawled urls

This is a somewhat safe approach; urls are unique throughout the web so chances are a hash function on top can prove to be successful. It however does not come without any drawbacks.

What if there are updates to the content crawled?

It is not uncommon for urls of websites to be generated based on the title of the source. It is the piece of text containing the most important information on the generated content; and the most SEO friendly one.

So what about updates to the titles? This can lead to updates to the url as well. So even though that is a rather straight-forward choice, special care should be taken to such updates in order to avoid duplicates.

Internal Identification Process

Time for the another approach; an internal identification process. This can be implemented either deploying an API endpoint responsible for assigning an ID to each resource collected (if your architecture follows the microservice one), or a simple method/function/bash script if you follow a monolithic approach.

The above suggested method has some very important pros; most important of them being its **blackbox way of working**. Once it has been perfected, you no longer have to worry about duplicates in your platform or assigning the same ID to 2 different resources.

But what about cons?

First and foremost, **time should be spent perfecting** such a mechanism. We cannot stress enough the important of ID assignment in (Big) Data Projects/Platforms, so you should definitely allow many hours (or story points) to such a project/task since it will be the backbone of pretty much everything you build.

Another drawback we should point out is the **rationale behind the identification** process. Basing it uniquely on the collected content can lead to duplicates as described in the previous case. Having some kind of complex process involving various factors (possibly differentiating based on the collected source) may prove more suitable.

Remote Source Identification

Let's switch our attention to the most challenging choice available. Time to attempt to identify the collected source's ID assignment method.

Why is it a challenging one?

It is because it requires knowledge of the remote source's tech stack. Although one may think of this trivial if the data collected is in an xls or csv format where identification is rather straight-forward what if a CMS is employed?

Knowledge of it should be present if one wants to successfully assign a unique ID able to avoid duplicates. For instance Drupal assigns a unique id to each piece of content (*nid*) always present in meta tags and by-default in CSS classes of article tags.

However not everything is a drawback for this method! If employed correctly one should never worry for her ID assignment; or almost never. Care should be taken only when **some major migration takes place** on the remote source's side, a rather infrequent case.

This concludes our analysis over various methods that can be employed as far as ID assignment in (Big) Data Platforms is concerned.

All of the above have pros and cons as is the case with everything out there. Similarly to every choice one has to make, you should weight these pros and cons.

BigDataGrapes suggested approach?

Apply some kind of hybrid approach, taking advantage of pros from various methods. It is what we have deployed so far in our platform and seems to work well.

The most important is to know your data and your sources. Keeping such knowledge in mind can prove crucial when assigning a unique identification method.

4.3 ORCHESTRATING ETL PIPELINES

As already described in 4.1 for the case of the Food Protection Pilot, we collect, translate and enrich global food safety data. This data covers:

- **food recalls** and **border rejections**,
- **price data** on agricultural commodities and animal products,
- **news items** related to food safety,
- **fraud cases**,
- **laboratory testing** performed by Food Safety Authorities worldwide,
- **inspections** and **warning letters** on food companies' plants and premises,
- **country level indicators** concerning food safety.

A heatmap for our daily cronjobs generated using [Cron Heatmap](#)

Figure 46: Heatmap for our daily cronjobs generated using Cron Heatmap

As you can imagine though, a number of workflows are involved in the process. Tasks triggering one another, signifying the collection, processing, enrichment of each of the close to 200M (taking into account the hierarchical model employed) data points that are present in our infrastructure.

There is a very important challenge that we need to take into account in such a Big Data Platform instance; **that of the overall orchestration.**

How did we tackle this challenge and what tools did we enlist for help?

How can we synchronize all these flows?

Back in 2018, when we first started implementing and deploying the Big Data Platform stack, cronjobs were an initial choice. Unfortunately popular choices like [Apache Airflow](#) and [Spotify's Luigi](#) had not gained that attention at the time!

What did we do? Bash scripts and crontab -e commands. Every source we track has its dedicated directory in our backend/processing servers and within each of these directories lies a run.sh script. This is the script that manages all the action. Every single task in each workflow triggered is managed by such a script, calling other scripts created with the responsibility to handle each task.

And this **run.sh** is triggered by crontab. For many of you accustomed with cronjobs, execution space of each cronjob may come as natural; we had to learn it the hard way. A base sample of the run.sh scripts that can be used.

```
#!/bin/bash

curr_dir="$( cd "$( dirname "${BASH_SOURCE[0]}" )" && pwd )"

cd ${curr_dir}

contents=$(cat ${curr_dir}/sync.lock)

if [ "$contents" != "0" ];then

    exit

fi

echo "1" > ${curr_dir}/sync.lock
```

```
# main code goes here

echo "0" > ${curr_dir}/sync.lock
```

The above depicted lines of code accompany every single script existent in our (dedicated) servers.

- The first thing we need to do is switch over to the directory of our to-be-crawled source. (lines: 2–3)
- Then we need to check if the previously triggered script has completed its work, this is done by checking the respective lockfile. (lines: 5–10)
- Once we are done with the main work we should update the lockfile for the next trigger of our script. (line: 14)

Depending on the source, **translation** endpoint triggering scripts may be present. **Text mining** or **text classification** workflows may take place with their respective scripts. All initiating calls to the respective projects and endpoints.

Say we are done with the collection and processing of each data record, we now have to let our **internal CMS** (Drupal) know of the new data. Time to sftp over there and upload the respective transformed and enriched records. That system will take care of the rest.

```
{

  "_id": ObjectId("5df60da920252e02c73c94bf"),

  "url": "https://www.inspection.gc.ca/about-the-cfia/newsroom/food-
recall-warnings/complete-listing/2019-12-
08/eng/1575846136193/1575846136974",

  "belongs": "cfia",

  "accessed": NumberLong(1576406528),

  "html_size": 23584,

  "text_size": 6093

}
```

Is this enough? You have most probably already guessed it. No. **What about data we have already processed?**

We should not stress our (already working at maximum capacity) servers any more than they have to; only new data needs to be taken into account. This is where our **MongoDB** kicks in; the place where all the raw data is stored, along with a collected on timestamp and a flag signifying whether or not a record has already been processed.

Sample of the metadata stored for each resource in our MongoDB instance

Is this enough? Again the (obvious) answer is no. **What about firewall limitations, fail2ban or overall crawler traffic restrictions?**

Although it would make our life way easier, firing up crawlers every minute towards each of the sources tracked regardless of the publishing rate may prove fatal in our endeavor. We need to configure our **ETL workflows** to be triggered only when chances are new data are present.

This although easily configurable through cron expressions requires some manual labor.

We need to dive into our data and identify the rate at which new records are published. Only then can we define an acceptable rate at which we can dispatch our workflows.

What about hardware limitations?

This is the most tricky question of all. Implementing and deploying a workflow capable of executing regardless the stress levels of a server is really challenging. Our choice at this point was splitting our workflow into **atomic operations** this ensures that even though a task or a workflow may not complete, no data loss will be observed since each new workflow triggered will always check for previous workflows' leftovers.

We should also consider some additional aspects:

- what about CPU/RAM intensive tasks?
- error logging?
- tools out there (Apache Airflow for instance!) that can make our life easier?

Since we are currently switching to **Apache Airflow** for our ETL pipelines, however let us stress at this point that all of the above are crucial. One cannot have a robust ETL pipeline if the above remarks are not addressed. And always researching and exploring new technologies and frameworks out there should be present in day to day tasks!

Just to give a quick overview in terms of numbers, in the current infrastructure of the Big Data Platform:

- **113 ETL workflow cronjobs** are present;
- on average workflows are triggered **once every 10 minutes**;
- **9 dedicated servers** are involved in this part of the infrastructure;
- **11 workflow jobs** have been switched **to Apache Airflow DAGs**;
- **1 Elastic Stack** instance (involving [Elasticsearch](#) & [Kibana](#) & [Metricbeat](#)) is employed to keep track of the health of our infrastructure.

4.4 AUTOMATING DATA ENGINEERING TASKS IN A BIG DATA PLATFORM

For every data engineer that is responsible for the operation and maintenance of a Big Data Platform instance there are 2 categories tasks:

- tasks that are challenging, meaning interesting, and
- tasks that are somewhat trivial.

To start with, **every task starts in the first category** and ends up in the second. Every single task each individual out there handles for the first time is a challenging one. One needs to perform it over and over again for it to fall under the category of the trivial tasks.

A lot of time is spend to conduct many times that same tasks such as:

- create a new ETL workflow
- performing the same operations
- calling the same endpoints
- saving results to a file system directory or to a storage engine
- moving data from one server to another

And there are many more questions where that came from and many ways to tackle each task. One can always click on Sublime, IntelliJ, PyCharm or whatever editor you favour and click on create new project.

Nothing compares with the excitement of a blank page! This is true only for **tasks never handled before though**. For all the rest you mainly copy-paste stuff from previous projects or Stack Overflow.

And although Stack Overflow will (hopefully) always be there for you to copy-paste, if you turn to previously implemented projects too often it may mean that there is some room for automation to take place.

- **Why copy-paste** the same code over and over again when you can *create a new API endpoint* to handle your requests?
- **Why manually** triggering a workflow when [ETL pipelines](#) are out there?
- **Why (s)ftp uploading** stuff with Filezilla when you can *write a script* to do that?
- **Why having reminders** to your calendar for backup ops when one or more *scripts can take care* of that?
- **Why manually** adding cronjobs when you can automatically *generate a DAG file* and put it in your [Apache Airflow](#) instance?

And although the above depicted list can most probably go on forever, there is a key take away message here: This can be fully automated.

- **A new project is always fun** to build and can help packing the same ops under one roof.
- **Cronjobs and crontabs** are there for you; all you need to do is create the script and pick the desired frequency.
- **Upload files & directories scripts** are easily writable and do not include the possibility of something going wrong.
- You may have more than 10 different storage engines; taking the time to write a **backup script** for each new instance means you never have to worry about it again, no small thing!
- **ETL workflow frameworks** can make your life way (way) easier, why not employ them?

If one attempts to always keep in mind the reusability and automation of processes then the result can be amazing. *Both in terms of code quality and component reusability, as well as in terms of robustness and bugless components.*

4.5 CONTAINER ORCHESTRATING AND DEPLOYMENT BEST PRACTICES FOR THE BIGDATAGRAPES GRAPHDB INSTANCE

In cases where a microservice architecture is used with multiple services having different functionalities and system requirements, the industry standard best practices suggest the use of a container orchestration system. In the case of BigDataGrapes, we have selected Kubernetes for its wide use in the field, comprehensive documentation, multiple plugins and all of the required functionalities. Following this approach, services are packed as docker images and can be automatically deployed from a docker repository. In order for Kubernetes to be able to monitor all deployed software and take action to restore services back to their operational state if needed, health check endpoints have been implemented.

Best practices suggest maintaining separate environments for development and production. Before services are released and deployed, they should pass through automated deployment and integration tests. A continuous integration system is used for this purpose, which in the case of BigDataGrapes is Jenkins. Once a newly developed software component is committed, the automated tests would run and in case of a success, the CI system would deploy the new artefacts.

For deployment, the de facto standard script for Kubernetes is Helm. This allows for easy deployment while allowing the deployment process to remain predictable and reliable.

5 Conclusions

In this document we performed the operational report of the BDG stack. The architecture of the stack, as described in D2.3, follows the microservice principles, leading us to document each layer's components based on the API endpoints they use, the work they perform, their expected parameters and input/output format of each.

This document outlines the final version of the software stack including the additional components developed and integrated into the stack since the previous version. It also presents the best practices for the deployment and maintenance of a Big Data Platform instance. Scalability tests and experiments on current and projected datasets have been performed as part of deliverables 7.2 and 7.3.